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INTERACTIVE METHODS OF TEACHING ENGLISH
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Abstract: The article discusses interactive methods of teaching English. The author describes the possibility of using some of these methods and techniques in an English lesson.

Key words: Interactive methods and techniques.

Currently, the state educational standard has high requirements for students. Short periods of mastering topics and a large amount of information are modern conditions for the general educational process. In order to implement such requests, new teaching methods must be found. Thanks to this, in the methodology of teaching English there has been a transition from a communicative approach to an interactive one. The interactive approach is one of the varieties of the communicative approach.

Interactive (“Inter” - mutual and “act” - to act) - means the ability to interact, to be in the mode of conversation, dialogue with someone. Those. Interactive learning is dialogue learning, during which the teacher interacts with students. [3, p.112].

The goal of interactive learning is that all participants in the lesson are in interaction. They are all actively involved in the learning process. The teacher serves as an assistant.

During dialogue, students learn to think, solve problems, make decisions and participate in discussions.

Modern pedagogy has many interactive methods. Among them are the following:

- Creative tasks;
- Educational games (role-playing games, educational games, etc.);
- Work in small groups, pairs, triplets (technique “2,4, together”);
- Carousel method;
- "Aquarium";
- “Brainstorming” or another name “brainstorming”;
- “Openwork saw”;
- "Brownian motion";
- Drawing up a mental map;
- “Choose a position”; • Debate; • Use of design methodology.

This list can be expanded, because... Each teacher can implement his own techniques and methods.

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The scope of one article does not make it possible to describe all interactive methods of teaching English, so we will consider only those that are used in practice.

Technique for drawing up a “Mind Map”. For the first time, the term was proposed by the British psychologist, author of the memorization technique, Tony Buzan. A map is a diagram that visually demonstrates various ideas, tasks, theses, related to each other and united by some common problem. The map allows you to cover the entire situation as a whole, as well as keep a large amount of information in your mind at the same time. Graphically, this map can be drawn in the form of a sun (in the center of which the main concept is indicated) from which rays of association extend. For example, a “mental map” of phrasal verbs. In the center is written a verb (to look - to look) from which the prepositions with which it is used radiate (to look for - to search; to look after - to take care; to look on - to count, etc.).

Another example of such a card is the Fishbone method. We are offered a fish skeleton. In the “head” we highlight the main problem, on the upper bones the students highlight the cause of the problem, and on the lower ones they write down facts that reflect the essence of the problem.

"Choose a position" method. Students are given a problem question where they must divide into 3 groups. The first group has a “For” point of view, the second “Against” and the third “I don’t know, haven’t decided on my own position.” Students are divided into groups and discuss the correctness of their position. One or more members of each group argue their position, after which there is a collective discussion of the problem and making the right decision. For example, discussing such a problem as “The Internet”.

Изначально учитель предоставляет ученикам фразу: Just a century ago we didn’t even know about computers and the Internet. But today we take them for granted and can’t imagine our life without these inventions, especially without internet... После чего в группах происходит обсуждение темы.

The most interesting method used in practice is the Sinkwine method.

Cinquain - (from French cinquains, English cinquain) is a five-line poetic form that arose in the USA at the beginning of the 20th century under the influence of Japanese poetry. Later it began to be used for didactic purposes, as an effective method of developing figurative speech, which allows you to quickly get results [1, p.105].

1. The first line is a designation of the topic using one word (noun);
2. Description of the topic (2 adjectives);
3. Description of the action, according to the proposed topic (3 verbs);

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4. Compiling a phrase of 4 words that expresses an attitude to the topic (different parts of speech);

5. Selection of a synonym for the topic (1 word).

We first carried out this method with 7th grade students. The topic we were studying at that moment was “Travel”. The work plan was as follows:

1. At the beginning of the lesson, the teacher should introduce students to the syncwine method and explain the writing rules.

2. Then 5-10 minutes are given for students to compose and exchange their options.

3. After which the syncwines are read and the most suitable options are selected. Here are examples of some work:

1. Traveling

2. Exciting, useful

3. To go, to fly, to swim

4. The best way to relax

5. My dream

I would like to note that interactivity will be more effective if multimedia technology is used in practice. Interactive methods also include presentations using various aids.

In conclusion, it is worth noting that the interactive teaching method increases motivation in learning English, the learning process becomes more interesting and exciting, and students feel freer. In addition, all methods and techniques develop communication skills, teach you to work in a team and listen to each other.

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